

ISic1226

I.Sicily inscription 1226

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Messina

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140712

1. ναύ [κλη] ροι (?)
2. Ὀλυμπις Ὑπερβόλου
3. Θεῦγνις □ Εὐβίου
4. Φρυνείδας Τεισάνδρου
5. [Δι]οκ[λη]ς ΥΣ[—]ΤΟΥ
6. □ Ἀριστόδαμος □ Εὐβίου
7. ΟΓΗΑΟυκος □ Εὐφε[ίδ]εος
8. [—]ΞΡΙΑ[ρ]χος Πε [ι] θ Ιάρχου ²⁶Πειθάρχου²⁶
9. Πεί[σ]ανδρος Ἀγάθωνος
10. [—]κ[λ]είδας Τεισάνδρου
11. [Απ]ο[λ]λόδωρος Ἀρχεδάμου
12. [Ζώ]πυρος Ναυκράτεος
13. [— —]ς Ὑπερ [βό]λου
14. [Αἴσ]χρων Ἀριστοξένου
15. [Α]φροδίται.
- 16.

Edition: PHI331409

1. ναύ[κλη]ροι
- 2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492832

EDCS 39101592

PHI 140712

PHI 331409

Bibliography

Gualtherus, G. 1624. Siciliæ obiacentium insular. et Bruttiorum antiquæ tabulæ, cum animadversionib. Messanae. At 2 no.3

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0401 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 36.0851

Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum. Berlin. At 3.5615 add

Bechtel, F., Collitz, H., Meister, R. C., Bezenberger, A. 1884-1915. Sammlung der griechischen Dialekt-Inschriften. Göttingen. At 5217

De Salvo, L. 1992. Economia privata e pubblici servizi nell'impero romano. I. Corpora naviculariorum. Messina.

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-22): ISic1226. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4385632>